

STANDARD QUALIFICATION PLAN FOR INCREASED INNOVATION

Graham D. Sims and Michael R.L. Gower

Materials Division, National Physical Laboratory
Teddington, Middlesex, TW11 0LW, UK
Email: graham.sims@npl.co.uk, web page: <http://www.npl.co.uk>

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ABSTRACT

Both composites suppliers and end-users are affected by the high cost of composite materials qualification. Qualifying a product against different user specifications causes time delays and increases the cost of introducing new materials. In addition, the provision of materials data for use in materials selection and preliminary design can be prohibitively costly for the material supplier due to repetition of the testing needed for different customers.

This paper reviews progress made towards a Standard Qualification Plan (SQP) aimed at reducing the substantial costs involved in qualifying fibre-reinforced plastic/composite materials. The SQP satisfies the minimum common requirements necessary to allow initial material selection, quality control and preliminary design to be undertaken. Specifically, it provides guidance on test method selection, panel and specimen preparation and machining, specimen sampling, conditioning and test environments, and statistical analysis of measured data. The results of associated round-robin validation exercises are briefly presented demonstrating the suitability and robustness of the test panel manufacture and the more critical test methods included in the SQP. This is important if the material supplier is to be allowed to release the initial property database based on their own tests alongside the material release.

Further qualification requirements, not met by the SQP, are included in an Extended Qualification Plan (EQP). In addition, non-aerospace sectors are interested in a "Lite" version being developed with the same core structure and test methods, but with reduced coverage.

Development of the SQP was supported by industry and regulatory authorities. Continued collaboration with, and support from industry and regulatory authorities, is required to encourage widespread adoption of the SQP. The SQP has been accepted as a new work item by ISO for progressing towards an international standard.

1 INTRODUCTION

Both composites suppliers and end-users are affected by the high cost of composite materials qualification. Qualifying a product against different user specifications, introducing new materials and finding data for materials selection and preliminary design can all be prohibitively costly due to repetition of testing. For example, one qualification programme for a new product **costs** £2 million to repeat ten times for different customers, rather than £0.13 million if one qualification could have been accepted by all. An estimate of a 40% increase in design cost was also given due to the delayed availability of design data.

Database recommendations were the subject of ISO 10,350-2 "*Plastics -- Acquisition and presentation of comparable single-point data -- Part 2: Long-fibre-reinforced plastics*" originally published in 2001. This document followed Part 1 covering moulding materials published in 1998. These standards used the same definition for "polymer composite" (i.e. long-fibre-reinforced plastics)

as applied to several of the test methods listed in Part 2. A long-fibre-reinforced thermoplastic or thermosetting material is defined as “where the reinforcement fibres are either discontinuous with a fibre length prior to processing greater than 7.5 mm (e.g. long fibre moulding compounds, chopped strand mat) or continuous (e.g. fabric, continuous-strand mat or unidirectional). Part 1 of this International Standard deals specifically with unreinforced and filled plastics, including those using fibres less than 7.5 mm in length.

This paper develops the scope of ISO 10,350-2 towards the preparation of a Standard Qualification Plan (SQP)[1] aimed at reducing the substantial costs involved in qualifying materials on behalf of suppliers, designers and end-users of composite materials. The SQP is aimed at satisfying the minimum common requirements necessary to allow initial material selection, quality control and preliminary design to be undertaken. Further qualification requirements, not met by the minimum SQP, are included in an Extended Qualification Plan (EQP). The SQP/EQP does not constitute a full qualification programme, rather, a standardised building block forming the initial stage of a qualification or certification programme. It is envisaged that the widespread use of this document for initial qualification, will not only lead to a reduction in qualification costs, but increase the availability of materials data and the use of composites in new applications.

Although the initial work by the National Physical Laboratory (NPL) was targeted at pre-preg material, predominately with carbon-fibre reinforcement, but not necessarily aerospace, now there is interest from other sectors (e.g. construction) for a reduced scope or “Lite” version. Both versions would have the same “core” requirements. Currently, the SQP draft has been accepted as an ISO new work item that will be revised to take account of similar initiatives, such as AGATE and NCAMP.

2 QUALIFICATION AND DATABASES

Figure 1: Chain of validation for composite products

Often when discussing qualification a pyramid of test methods will be used with the number of tests decreasing as the complexity of the “article” tested increases towards the final complete product. An alternative view is a ladder or chain (see Figure 1), whereby the alternating dependence of specification and test methods standards at each level is clear. Each specification or validation step needs to be underpinned by suitable test and evaluation methods, not forgetting the use of modelling and simulation. These steps are relevant to all applications where the composites perform primary and

secondary structural roles. In addition, consideration needs to be given to the maintenance, repair and in-service inspection requirements, once the product is in-service, an aspect often overlooked in product standards.

Reviewing these individual steps, the current situation is as follows:

- **Constituent Materials Test Methods** - The evaluation of the constituent materials is covered by a fairly complete set of EN ISO and ISO test standards for fibres and resins. ISO has developed harmonised fibre test methods, so that there is no requirement to wait for a new standard for a new fibre, providing the technical requirements of the existing standard are met.
- **Constituent Materials Specifications** - The specification of the constituent materials is fairly well covered in ISO standards and by SAE standards. There are more extensive specifications for the thermoset and thermoplastic matrices due to their use as unreinforced plastics.
- **Moulding and Prepreg Test Methods** – Limited methods available for properties related to mouldings, such as, ISO 17771: *Plastics -- Thermoset moulding compounds -- Determination of the degree of fibre wetting in SMC*.
- **Moulding and Prepreg Specifications** – Limited coverage such as, for SMC (ISO 8605: *Textile-glass-reinforced plastics -- Sheet moulding compound (SMC) -- Basis for a specification*),
- **Laminate Test Methods** - A full range of test methods exist in most major series such as ISO, EN ISO, EN Aerospace and ASTM. Further details will be covered in the next section.
These methods now include another potential “step”, with coupon tests including a stress concentration such as a hole (tested in compression or tension, or by pin loading) or as a small plate specimen impact loaded to cause barely-visible impact damage (i.e. BVID) and then tested in compression. These methods are covered in the EQP.
- **Composite Specifications** – Limited “alloy” type specification due to the design freedom that enables laminates to use different fibres, fibre formats, alignment etc. Performance based specification for pultruded profiles - EN 13,706: *Reinforced plastics composites. Specifications for pultruded profiles*.
- **Structural Element Test Methods** – No standards currently exist, although there is research at NPL towards the characterisation of the performance of generic complex test elements, such as stiffened beam and panels.

The next three steps are more specifically related to the application and cases where composites will not be the only material considered. However, there are cases where regulations continue to prevent the application of composites.

- **Sub-Component Approval** -
- **Full Scale Test methods** –
- **Final Product Approval** –

There are an increasing number of product standards such as, EN 40-7: Lighting columns. Requirements for fibre-reinforced polymer composite lighting columns; ISO 11119-4: Gas cylinders of composite construction and ISO 14692-1: Petroleum and natural gas industries - Glass-reinforced plastics (GRP) piping.

- **Approved Maintenance Procedures** – these are not well established in general standards.
- **NDE Procedures** – C-scan ultrasonics most established. Need to introduce procedures for more novel techniques, such as,

3 DEVELOPMENT OF THE STANDARD QUALIFICATION PLAN

Based on the results of an industrial consultation exercise and review of other documents, test methods identified as the highest priority formed the SQP and those of lower priority formed the EQP. All of the physical/chemical property tests that were surveyed have been included in the SQP, as it was felt that the vast majority of these properties were already released with the supplier’s materials data. The cured mechanical property test methods selected for the SQP consist of tensile, compressive, shear and flexural tests (in addition to fibre and resin volume fraction), giving ultimate strength, failure strain, elastic modulus and Poisson’s ratio data. Additional test methods deemed non-essential for initial materials qualification but that can be used to generate specific, application dependent data, were grouped into the EQP. The test data presentation followed ISO 10,350-2 recommendations.

The prescribed qualification test regime (using the test methods listed in Section 4.2) is detailed in the SQP procedure, as shown in Figure 2. The tables set out the numbers of batches of specimens per test method, per test condition. Specimens shall be prepared and tested from either 1 or 3 batches of material depending on the criticality of the data (i.e. the importance of the data for use in design, material selection etc. The applied environmental conditions include -55°C, Room temperature, 70°C, 125°C (180°C cured systems only) and testing after conditioning at 70°C/85 % RH for 1000 hrs

Property	Symbol	Standard	Unit	Test Condition						Test conditions and supplementary instructions
				DRY				70°C/85% RH		
				-55°C	RT	70°C	125°C*	RT	70°C	
16 Fibre and resin volume fraction	V _f	ISO 14127 and ISO 1183	%		3					ISO 1183 for density
	V _r		%		3					
17 Tension	σ _{M11}	Unidirectional BS EN ISO 527-5	MPa	1	3	1			1	Refer to standard for specimen dimensions and test details. () – not required for balanced fabrics
	σ _{M22}		MPa	1	1	(1)			(1)	
	E ₁₁		GPa	1	3	1			1	
	E ₂₂		GPa	1	1	(1)			(1)	
	ε _{M11}	%	1	3	1			1		
	ε _{M22}	%	1	1	(1)			(1)		
	V ₁₂		1							
	V ₁₃		1							
	V ₂₁		1							
	V ₂₃		1							
	18 Compression	σ _{M11}	ISO 14126 unidirectional, multidirectional	MPa	1	3	1			
σ _{M22}		MPa			1	(1)			1	
E ₁₁		GPa		1	3	1			3	
E ₂₂		GPa			1	(1)			1	
ε _{M11}		%		1	3	1			3	
ε _{M22}		%			1	(1)			1	
19 Shear ≈45° tension	τ _{M12}	BS EN ISO 14129	MPa	1	3	1	1	1	1	
	γ _{M12}		%	1	3	1	1	1	1	
	G ₁₂		GPa	1	3	1	1	1	1	
20 ILSS – through thickness	τ _{M1}	BS EN ISO 14130	MPa	1	3	1	3	1	3	
	τ _{M2}		MPa		1	1				
21 Flexural	σ _{M11}	BS EN ISO 14125	MPa		3					Refer to standard for specimen dimensions and test details. Provide details of which method used: Method A (3 point flexure) and Method B (4 point flexure)
	σ _{M22}		MPa		3					
	E ₁₁		MPa		3					
	E ₂₂		MPa		3					
	G ₁₃		GPa		3					

Figure 2 Standard Qualification Plan - Cured mechanical properties - Batch requirements

Specimens are taken from 3 batches of material in order for measured values to be as representative as possible of the material being tested and these batches should be taken from the production of the material over an extended timescale. In addition, to account for the processing variability associated with panel manufacture, two panels are fabricated from each material batch, using independent lay-up and cure processes. Five specimens per panel are extracted for each test method (N.B. some tests use < 5 specimens), giving a total of 30 specimens per property for a particular test environment – see Figure 3. In a similar manner, those properties measured using only 1 batch of material shall be determined from 10 specimens prepared from 2 panels (prepared using independent lay-up and cure processes).

Figure 3: Batch, panel and specimen traceability

The properties measured were grouped in two sets, uncured and cured:

UNCURED PROPERTIES

- 1 Mass per unit area - ISO 10352
- 2 Fibre mass per unit area - EN 2559
- 3 Resin and fibre volume fraction - ISO 11667
- 4 Gel time - ISO 15040
- 5 Resin flow - ISO 15034
- 6 Glass transition temperature (DSC) - ISO 11357-2
- 7 Percentage of volatile content - EN 2558
- 8 Density of fibre - ISO 10119
- 9 Analysis by DSC - ISO 11357-1
- 10 Density of resin - ISO 1675

CURED PROPERTIES

- 11 Coefficient of thermal expansion - EN 821-1
- 12 Moisture uptake - EN 3615 (Conditioning in 70°C/85% atmosphere)
- 13 Moisture uptake - EN 2378 (Immersion in water at 70°C)
- 14 Glass transition temperature by DMA - ISO 6721-11 °C
- 15 Cured ply thickness - ISO 16012.2
- 16 Fibre and resin volume fraction - ISO 14127 and ISO 1183
- 17 Tension – Unidirectional - EN ISO 527-5 / Multidirectional EN ISO 527-4
- 18 Compression - ISO 14126
- 19 Shear $\pm 45^\circ$ tension - EN ISO 14129
- 20 ILSS – through thickness - EN ISO 14130
- 21 Flexural - EN ISO 14125

4 VALIDATION OF THE STANDARD QUALIFICATION PLAN

In developing the SQP, the robustness of different stages was examined, which is particularly important when an individual company (i.e. the material supplier) could be tasked to provide the agreed database. The stages assessed were manufacture of the test plate and performance of t-test statistical methods. These exercises were conducted separately. For the test methods, the final specimens were supplied centrally by NPL.

4.1 Validation of test plate manufacture

Figure 4: Elements of test programme

At the coupon level of testing, it is necessary to cut coupons or specimens from the product or from a test panel. ISO 1268: Fibre-reinforced plastics – Methods of producing test plates (provide title) covers the manufacture of test plates for all current process routes for long-fibre composites (see Table 1). Further parts are expected as new processing routes become established – see also Figure 4.

Part 4 on pre-pregs, drafted by NPL, is the only part that includes precision data. The data was based on the results of a round-robin on panel manufacture. NPL supplied pre-preg direct from the manufacturer to participants for fabricating panels of different size and thickness. The panels were then sent to NPL where a series of specimens were prepared from each panel and subsequently tested. Using one site, NPL, for preparing the specimens and undertaking the testing limited the uncertainty introduced by this stage. The results showed that participants could prepare panels to a consistent and high standard [2].

Part No.	ISO 1268: Fibre-reinforced plastics – Methods of producing test plates
1	General principles
2	Contact and spay moulding
3	Wet compression moulding
4	Moulding of preimpregnates
5	Filament moulding
6	Pultrusion moulding
7	Resin Transfer moulding
8	Moulding of SMC/BMC
9	Moulding of GMT/STC
10	Injection moulding of BMC + long fibre compounds - general principles + multipurpose specimens
11	Injection moulding of BMC and long-fibre moulding compounds -- Small plates

Table 1: Individual parts of EN ISO 1268 for test plate manufacture

4.2 Validation of Test Methods

A round-robin exercise was undertaken with the aim of increasing confidence in the data measured by any organisation using the SQP/EQP and associated test methods. Tests were performed on two 120°C cure carbon fibre-epoxy pre-preg materials. Results from the round-robin were analysed according to ISO 5725: 1994, *Accuracy (trueness and precision) of measurement methods and results*

(using 95% confidence limits) in order to assess the repeatability (measure of within site scatter) and reproducibility (measure of between site scatter) of 5 test methods selected from the SQP and to generate materials data for possible future inclusion in a materials database.

The definitions of repeatability and reproducibility that contribute to the increasingly mandatory precision statement in a standard are:

- **repeatability conditions:** Conditions where independent test results are obtained with the same method on identical test items in the same laboratory by the same operator using the same equipment within short intervals of time.
- **reproducibility conditions:** Conditions where test results are obtained with the same method on identical test items in different laboratories with different operators using different equipment.

Test panels were manufactured at NPL according to the fabrication method given in ISO 1268-4 and following material supplier's guidance. All panels were autoclave cured. Specimens were extracted from test panels in accordance with ISO 2818: *Plastics -- Preparation of test specimens by machining*. Specimens were machined to the dimensions and tolerances given in the appropriate test standards. Specific guidance on machining of composites is given in GPG 38 [2] and SAE Aerospace Information Note AIR 5367 - *Plastics -- Preparation of test specimens by machining*. Machining operations were performed using a Bennett diamond grit coated circular saw, with water used as a coolant/lubricant.

The test standards used for the round-robin validation exercise were:

- EN ISO 527-5: *Plastics - Determination of tensile properties - Part 5: Test conditions for unidirectional fibre-reinforced plastic composites* (see also Part 1),
- EN ISO 14126: *Fibre-reinforced plastic composites - Determination of compressive properties in the in-plane direction*,
- EN ISO 14125: *Fibre-reinforced plastic composites - Determination of flexural properties*,
- EN ISO 14130: *Fibre-reinforced plastic composites - Determination of apparent interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) by short-beam method*,
- ISO 6721-11: *Plastics - Determination of dynamic mechanical properties - Part 11: Glass transition temperature*,

The four mechanical test methods selected are recommended tests in the SQP. The dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) test was included in this round-robin, as it was a test recommended to be included following industry review of the draft SQP document.

All specimens were of unidirectional (UD) lay-up and the following properties were measured by participants (see Figure 4); maximum value of tensile stress (σ_{Mt11}), tensile modulus (E_{t11}), Poisson's ratio (ν_{12}), maximum value of compressive stress (σ_{Mc11}), compressive modulus (E_{c11}), maximum value of interlaminar shear stress (σ_{M1}), maximum value of flexural strength (σ_{Mf11}), flexural modulus (E_{f11}), glass transition temperature (T_g , plus T_{onset} , T_{loss} , and $T_{\tan \delta}$).

Figure 5: Repeatability and reproducibility standard deviations as percentages of mean values

In general, the results of the round-robin exercise, see Figure 5, showed that a range of test methods selected from the SQP document are suitably robust for inclusion in such a materials qualification plan. Details of a number of salient findings from the exercise now follow:

- Tensile (strength, modulus and Poisson's ratio), flexure (strength and modulus) and interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) tests all showed very good repeatability and reproducibility values (close to, or better than, 5% of their respective means).
- The known variability of compression testing was reflected with fairly high values of repeatability and reproducibility for the compressive strength results. Compressive modulus results were lower (i.e. less than 10% of the mean). However, it is noted that the number of sites able to perform the compression tests was low. In addition, in order to ascertain whether Euler buckling has taken place during loading, it is essential that two strain measurements are made on opposite faces of each specimen.
- The DMA results showed very low repeatability, but comparatively high reproducibility values due to deficiencies in temperature measurement using various DMA equipment. It is noted that DMA is increasingly being considered as an alternative to quality control tests, such as flexure and ILSS, however concern exists over using DMA for this purpose due to the poor values of reproducibility presently inherent in the method, as verified in this round-robin exercise and in previous exercises organised by NPL [3].

5 CONCLUSIONS

Validation of the SQP developed with industry, academia and regulators support provides a valuable starting point for qualification of polymer composites. The results of the associated round-robin validation exercise demonstrates the suitability and robustness of test methods included in the SQP, and it is anticipated that this will encourage the use of the procedure and increase confidence in the data measured by users. It is envisaged that the widespread use of this document for initial qualification, will not only lead to a reduction in qualification costs, but increase the availability of materials data and the use of composites in new applications. The ability of participants to manufacture test panels to a consistent standard was also confirmed.

One key area for the future is to develop reduced or “lite” versions of the qualification plans for other industrial sectors using different material types and formats, and operating under different in-service conditions.

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